

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the sixth regular issue of 2024. In this issue, 6 papers cover various topical aspects of computer science by 19 authors from 7 countries: Brazil, Chile, France, India, Saudi Arabia, Tunisia, and Turkey. In an ongoing effort to further strengthen our journal, I would like to expand the editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a strong publication record, you are welcome to apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and trends.

As always, I would like to thank all authors for their sound research and the editorial board and our guest reviewers for their extremely valuable review effort and suggestions for improvement. These contributions, together with the generous support of the consortium members, help to maintain the quality of our journal.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce the following 6 accepted articles: George Marsicano, Edna Dias Canedo, Glauco V. Pedrosa, Cristiane S. Ramos, and Rejane M. da C. Figueiredo from Brazil look in their study into digital transformation of public services in a startup-based environment by 23 focus groups and 175 participants in total. Mauricio Solar and Pablo Aguirre from Chile discuss their research on 3D chest CT processes applying a ResNet-50 model to which a new dimension of information has been added, namely a simple autoencoder. In a collaborative work between researchers from Tunisia and France, Rakia Saidi, Fethi Jarray, and Didier Schwab propose in their article a cross-encoder neural network (Cross-BERT-GRU) to deal with the semantic similarity of Arabic sentences that benefits from both the strong contextual understanding of BERT and the sequential modeling capabilities of GRU. Also in a collaborative research between institutions from Tunisia and Saudi Arabia, Nozha Jlidi, Sameh Kouni, Olfa Jemai, and Tahani Bouchrika present their research on MediaPipe with GNN for human activity recognition. G.V.Vidya Lakshmi and S. Gopikrishnan from India look into missing values research for the IoT domain and in particular present IMD-MP technique that improves imputation accuracy for big data analysis in IoT applications based on spatial-temporal correlations. Last but not least, F. Didem Alay, Nagehan İlhan, and M. Tahir Güllüoğlu address in their article a comparative study of data mining methods for solar radiation and temperature forecasting models.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
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